

POLYNOMIAL INEQUALITIES FOR MULTIPARTITE QUANTUM SYSTEMS IN MIXED STATES

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Abstract

Entanglement in a multipartite quantum system represents non-local correlations between the system parts. This phenomenon is not affected by the action of a symmetry group, which acts separately on each part of the multipartite composite system. The space of the invariants of the action is a natural domain of the definition for all possible measures of the entanglement. Allowed values of the invariants are restricted by a set of inequalities, which is analyzed in this paper. The inequalities ensue from the semipositivity and Hermiticity of the density matrix for the system as well as from the orbit space description in terms of the invariant theory.

1. Introduction

An extraordinary phenomenon—entanglement—is the cornerstone of the modern theory of quantum computing and quantum information [1, 2]. Basically, the term entanglement is understood as an exposition of diverse nonlocal correlations between parts of a composite multipartite quantum system, which have no classical analogue. From both theoretical and experimental points of view, the major problem consists in the definition of entanglement measures.

It is shown [3] that, from the mathematical point of view, characteristics of entanglement can be understood in terms of the classical theory of invariants [4, 5]. The key observation is that there exists a special group G consisting of the so-called *local unitary transformations* [3]. It means that G acts separately on every part of the multipartite composite system and does not affect the nonlocal correlations. For example, consider a binary quantum system composed of two subsystems of dimensions n_1 and n_2 . The local unitary group $G = \text{SU}(n_1) \times \text{SU}(n_2)$ acts on density matrix ρ adjointly,

$$(\text{Ad } g)\rho = g \rho g^{-1}, \quad g \in G \subset \text{SU}(n_1 \times n_2).$$

Therefore, any characteristic of the entanglement is a function on the quotient space ρ/G and, consequently, a function of G -invariant polynomials $p(\rho)$ in the elements of the density matrix ρ . Suppose that we know the integrity basis $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q\}$ for the invariant ring¹

¹ Basically, there are algebraic relations between the elements of the basis called syzygies.

$$\mathbb{R}[\varrho]^G = \mathbb{R}[p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q], \quad (1.2)$$

which means that any G-invariant polynomial $P(\varrho)$ is a polynomial in p_k from the basis. So, the domain of definition of all possible entanglement measures is the image of the map from ϱ/G into a submanifold X in the real space \mathbb{R}^q , where p_k take their values.

In this paper, we present a complete set of polynomial inequalities defining the semi-algebraic structure of X and show that they stem from two sources:

- (i) positive semi-definiteness and Hermiticity of the density matrix ϱ ,
- (ii) positive semi-definiteness of the Gram matrix [6] of gradient vectors to level surfaces $p_k(\varrho) = \text{const}$ for each p_k from the integrity basis \mathcal{P} for $\mathbb{R}[\varrho]^G$ [7].

Their formulation is given in Sections 2 and 3, respectively. In Section 4, we illustrate them using the example of a two-qubit system described by a 5-parameter density matrix.

2. Inequalities from the Properties of Density Matrices

•Density matrices

Following the ideas of John von Neuman [8] and Lev Landau [9], a quantum system is described by the self-adjoint, positive semi-definite *density operator* acting in the Hilbert space of the system. Given a non-relativistic n -dimensional quantum system, Hilbert space \mathcal{H} is the n -dimensional complex space \mathbb{C}^n and the density operator can be identified with $n \times n$ Hermitian, unit trace, positive semi-definite matrix ϱ , which is referred to as the *density matrix*.

Constraints to the density operator due to semi-positive definiteness have been imposed in the sixtieth of the last century in studying the production and decay of resonant states in strong interaction processes [10]. Nowadays, the quantum computing and the theory of quantum information reveal a new role of these constraints; recently, they have been derived once again [11, 12]².

To formulate the semi-definiteness property, let us choose the Bloch representation of a density matrix [15] for n -level quantum system:

$$\varrho = \frac{1}{n} \left(\mathbb{I}_n + \sqrt{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \sum_{i=1}^{n^2-1} \xi_i \lambda_i \right) \quad (2.1)$$

where $(n^2 - 1)$ is the dimensional Bloch vector $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^{(n^2-1)}$ is contracted with elements $\lambda_i, i = 1, \dots, (n^2 - 1)$ of the Hermitian basis of $\mathfrak{su}(n)$ Lie algebra.

•Positivity of density matrices

A necessary and sufficient condition for the Hermitian matrix to be positive is that coefficients S_k of the characteristic equation

$$|\mathbb{I}_n x - \varrho| = x^n - S_1 x^{n-1} + S_2 x^{n-2} - \dots + (-1)^n S_n = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

should be non-negative [10]:

$$\varrho \geq 0 \iff S_k \geq 0 \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (2.3)$$

² In our publication [13] the positivity conditions for density operators was analyzed in the context of their consequences for integrity basis of $SU(2) \otimes SU(2)$ polynomial invariants ring as well as for entanglement characteristics of mixed qubit states [14].

This statement is based on the Descartes theorem [16] about the number of positive roots of a polynomial equation. The expressions for coefficients S_k in terms of the traces

$$t_k = \text{tr}(\rho^k) \quad (2.4)$$

are given by the determinants

$$S_k = \frac{1}{k!} \begin{vmatrix} t_1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ t_2 & t_1 & 2 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ t_3 & t_2 & t_1 & 3 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ t_{k-1} & t_{k-2} & t_{k-3} & t_{k-4} & \ddots & k-1 \\ t_k & t_{k-1} & t_{k-2} & t_{k-3} & \cdots & t_1 \end{vmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

In addition, from restrictions (2.3), there are upper bounds on S_k due to the normalization condition $\text{tr}(\rho) = 1$, $\text{tr}(\rho^k) \leq 1$ for $k \geq 2$. Note that the equality fulfils for pure states and the maximal values of S_k are achieved for the equal eigenvalues of density matrices.

Finally, the positive semi-definiteness and normalizability conditions for density matrices of n -level system can be written as the following set of inequalities

$$0 \leq \frac{k!n^{k-1}S_k}{(n-1)(n-2)\cdots(n-k+1)} \leq 1, \quad k = 2, \dots, n. \quad (2.6)$$

•Hermicity of density matrices

Since matrix ρ is Hermitian, all its eigenvalues are real numbers. However, conditions (2.3) for coefficients S_k do not explicitly recognize that the characteristic equation (2.2) should not have any complex roots. For the case of all distinct roots, the necessary and sufficient condition providing reality of the roots λ_i is the positivity of the discriminant

$$\text{Discr} = \prod_{i < j} (\lambda_i - \lambda_j)^2$$

which is considered as a function of traces (2.4)

$$\text{Discr} = \begin{vmatrix} d & t_1 & t_2 & \cdots & t_{n-1} \\ t_1 & t_2 & t_3 & \cdots & t_{n-2} \\ t_2 & t_3 & t_4 & \cdots & t_{n-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ t_{n-1} & t_{n-2} & t_{n-1} & \cdots & t_{2n-2} \end{vmatrix} \geq 0. \quad (2.7)$$

To take into account the case of the multiple roots, we should demand the positivity of all principal minors of Discr. Dependence of the discriminant on the trace invariants up to order $2n-2$ as pointed in the left side of (2.7) assumes that all the higher trace invariants t_k with $k > n$ are expressed via polynomials in t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n using the Cayley-Hamilton theorem.

The summary of this section is as follows. The set of inequalities originating from Hermicity (2.7) and semi-positivity (2.6) requirements on density matrices can be formulated in terms of traces t_k . Note that t_k are the invariants of the group $SU(n)$ acting globally on the entire system.

3. Inequalities from the Invariant Theory

The inequalities stemming from the invariant theory should be formulated in terms of the invariants relative to the group $G \subset SU(n)$ of local unitary transformations. Again, consider a binary quantum system composed from two subsystems of dimensions n_1 and n_2 with local group $G = SU(n_1) \times SU(n_2)$, $n_1 \times n_2 = n$. The adjoint action (1.1) of the local group can be linearized [17] if we represent density matrix ρ as vector $\vec{\rho}$ in the real space $\mathbb{R}^{(n^2-1)}$ and consider the linear transformation

$$\vec{\rho} \rightarrow \vec{\rho}' = L\vec{\rho}$$

with the linear operator $L \in G \otimes \bar{G}$, where the overlined \bar{G} denotes the complex conjugate of G . The property being linear of the adjoint action makes possible application of the invariant theory and, in particular, application of algorithmic methods for construction of the integrity basis. The local invariant ring $\mathbb{R}[\rho]^G$ has a much more complicated structure than the invariant ring $\mathbb{R}[\rho]^{SU(n)}$. A complete description of it has been given up to now only for the simplest case $G = SU(2) \times SU(2)$ [18]. Note that traces t_k (2.4), being invariants of group $SU(n)$, are polynomials in terms of G -invariants. Consequently, conditions (2.6) and (2.7) restrict the possible values of G -invariants.

Let us discuss additional inequalities that follow from the invariant theory. Let K be a compact Lie group acting on a n -dimensional linear space V . Assume that

$$\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q\}, \tag{3.1}$$

is a set of real homogeneous polynomials that forms the integrity basis invariant ring

$$\mathbb{R}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]^K = \mathbb{R}[p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q], \tag{3.2}$$

The elements of \mathcal{P} define the polynomial mapping:

$$P: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q, \quad (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q). \tag{3.3}$$

Since the integrity basis elements p_k are constants along the orbits of K , the P map induces a homeomorphism of the orbit space V/G and its image X , i.e., $V/G \simeq X$ [7]. Generally speaking, there are polynomial relations $h(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q)$ between p_k forming the syzygy ideal $I_{\mathcal{P}}$ of \mathcal{P} (3.1):

$$I_{\mathcal{P}}(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q) = \{h \in \mathbb{R}[p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q] : h(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q) = 0 \text{ in } \mathbb{R}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]\}. \tag{3.4}$$

This means that all $h(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q)$ are identically zero when p_k are considered as functions of coordinates x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n in V . The syzygies define a submanifold $Z \subset \mathbb{R}^q$ consisting of the locus of common zeros of all elements in $I_{\mathcal{P}}$. Finally, we should introduce a symmetric $q \times q$ -matrix Grad whose elements are the inner products of the gradients $\text{grad}(p_i)$ to the level surfaces $p_i = \text{const}_i$ in V :

$$\text{Grad}_{ij} = (\text{grad}(p_i), \text{grad}(p_j)). \tag{3.4}$$

The elements of the Grad -matrix can be written as polynomials on generators p_i of the integrity basis [7].

A theorem due to Procesi and Schwarz [19] states that image X of orbit space V/K is a subset of Z and is defined by the set of inequalities expressing semipositivity of the matrix Grad:

$$\text{Grad} \geq 0. \quad (3.5)$$

The rigorous proof of the theorem is rather involved; however, the key point is quite simple. Gradients $\text{grad}(p_i)$ form the basis of the normal space to tangent space $T\mathcal{O}$ of the K -orbit \mathcal{O} . They should be linearly independent in order the normal space has right dimension³ equal to the difference $\dim V - \dim \mathcal{O}$. Note that this difference is just the number of algebraically independent invariants among the integrity basis elements. Since matrix Grad is the Gram matrix for the set of the vectors $\text{grad}(p_i)$, its positivity ensure us that these vectors are linearly independent according to the well-known theorem of linear algebra (see, for example, [6] chapter IX, §3).

The Grad-matrix can be represented as a product $\text{Grad} = J \cdot J^T$ where $J = (\partial p_i / \partial x_j)$ is the Jacobian of polynomial map P . It is shown [19] that J generalizes Vandermonde matrix Δ for the roots of a polynomial equation. Therefore, if we consider the ring of $SU(n)$ invariants of density matrix ϱ , then the Grad-matrix is similar to the discriminant $\text{Discr} = \Delta \cdot \Delta^T$, as shown by explicit calculations in [20].

4. Illustrative Example

4.1 Invariant Ring of a Two-Qubit System

We consider a composite system which consists of two qubits; that is, each subsystem has two quantum levels. It is useful to represent the density matrix of the system in the so-called Fano form:

$$\varrho = \frac{1}{4} \left(\mathbb{I}_2 \otimes \mathbb{I}_2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i \sigma_i \otimes \mathbb{I}_2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 b_i \mathbb{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_i + \sum_{i,j=1}^3 c_{ij} \sigma_i \otimes \sigma_j \right) \quad (4.1)$$

where 3-component vectors $\vec{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ and $\vec{b} = (b_1, b_2, b_3)$ are Bloch vectors of constituent qubits, $\sigma_i, i = 1, 2, 3$, are the Pauli matrices making up the basis of the Lie algebra $\mathfrak{su}(2)$:

$$\sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.2)$$

Information about the correlations between qubits is encoded in the matrix $C = (c_{ij}), i, j = 1, 2, 3$.

The G group of the local unitary transformations for this system is the tensor product $SU(2) \otimes SU(2) \subset SU(4)$ and acts in the following way:

$$\varrho \mapsto (SU(2) \otimes SU(2)) \cdot \varrho \cdot (SU(2) \otimes SU(2))^\dagger,$$

where the dagger states for the Hermitian conjugate.

The local invariant ring $\mathbb{R}[\varrho]^G$ consists of real homogeneous polynomials in fifteen variables a_i, b_j, c_{ij} . The homogeneity holds separately for each set of variables a_i, b_j, c_{ij} and every invariant can be labeled by degrees of variables from this three sets. So, an invariant

³ Here, we consider only the special case of the regular orbits of the adjoint action.

$C_{(s\ t\ q)}$ is a sum of monomials containing s variables a_i , t variables b_j , and q variables c_{ij} . The number of algebraically independent invariants is as follows:

$$15 - 2 \dim SU(2) = 9.$$

The integrity basis of the ring $\mathbb{R}[\varrho]^G$ contains 15 additional invariants required for the Hironaka representation of $\mathbb{R}[\varrho]^G$ [18]. Below, we list the invariants of lowest orders relevant for our simple example given in the following subsections. The completely antisymmetric symbol ϵ_{ijk} represents the structure constant tensor of $SU(2)$ group. We use the Einstein index summation convention.

Degree Invariants

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \quad & C_{200} = a_i a_i, \quad C_{020} = b_j b_j, \quad C_{002} = c_{ij} c_{ij} \\ 3 \quad & C_{111} = a_i b_j c_{ij}, \quad C_{003} = \frac{1}{3} \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{pqr} c_{ip} c_{jq} c_{kr} \\ 4 \quad & C_{202} = a_i a_j c_{ip} c_{jp}, \quad C_{022} = b_i b_j c_{pi} c_{pj}, \quad C_{004} = c_{ip} c_{iq} c_{jp} c_{jq} \\ & C_{112} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{pqr} a_i b_p c_{jq} c_{kr} \\ 5 \quad & C_{113} = a_i b_p c_{ij} c_{kj} c_{kp} \\ 6 \quad & C_{204} = a_i a_p c_{ij} c_{kj} c_{kq} c_{pq}, \quad C_{024} = b_i b_p c_{ji} c_{jk} c_{qk} c_{qp} \end{aligned}$$

4.2 5-Parameter Subset of Density Matrices

Let us denote five Fano parameters

$$a_3 = \alpha, \quad b_3 = \beta, \quad c_{11} = \gamma_1, \quad c_{22} = \gamma_2, \quad c_{33} = \gamma_3,$$

and equate all others to zero. We get the following density matrix

$$\varrho = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + \alpha + \beta + \gamma_3 & 0 & 0 & \gamma_1 - \gamma_2 \\ 0 & 1 + \alpha + \beta + \gamma_3 & \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 & 1 + \alpha + \beta + \gamma_3 & 0 \\ \gamma_1 - \gamma_2 & 0 & 0 & 1 + \alpha + \beta + \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.3)$$

which belongs to the class of the so-called X-states because nonzero elements are placed only on the diagonals. The invariant ring for these states is studied in [21]. There are only 12 non-zero local invariants in this case:

Degree Invariants

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \quad & C_{200} = \alpha^2, \quad C_{020} = \beta^2, \quad C_{002} = \gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2 + \gamma_3^2 \\ 3 \quad & C_{111} = \alpha \beta \gamma_3, \quad C_{003} = \gamma_1 \gamma_2 \gamma_3 \\ 4 \quad & C_{202} = \alpha^2 \gamma_3^2, \quad C_{022} = \beta^2 \gamma_3^2, \quad C_{004} = \gamma_1^4 + \gamma_2^4 + \gamma_3^4, \quad C_{112} = \alpha \beta \gamma_1 \gamma_2 \\ 5 \quad & C_{113} = \alpha \beta \gamma_3^3 \\ 6 \quad & C_{204} = \alpha^2 \gamma_3^4, \quad C_{024} = \beta^2 \gamma_3^4 \end{aligned}$$

There are only five algebraically independent invariants among them. We choose the lowest order invariants

$$C_{200}, C_{020}, C_{002}, C_{111}, C_{003}$$

and introduce special notations for the following combinations of them to simplify the representation of the inequalities in terms of these invariants:

$$C_2 := C_{200} + C_{020} + C_{002}, \quad C_3 := C_{111} - C_{003}, \quad D := \frac{C_{200} C_{020}}{C_{111}^2}.$$

The complete set of the inequalities is as follows:

- Semipositivity of density matrix ϱ :

$$0 \leq C_2 \leq 3, \quad 0 \leq C_2 - 2C_3 \leq 1, \quad (4.4)$$

$$0 \leq D^2((1 - C_2)^2 + 8C_3) - 4(C_2D + C_3^2D^3 - 1) \leq 1. \quad (4.5)$$

- Semipositivity of discriminant Disc:

$$0 \leq C_2(C_2D - 1) + C_3^2D^2(C_2D - 9), \quad (4.6)$$

$$0 \leq (C_2D - 1)^2 - 4C_3^2D^3. \quad (4.7)$$

- Semipositivity of matrix Grad:

$$0 \leq (C_{002}D - 1)^2 - 4C_{003}^2D^3. \quad (4.8)$$

To visualize the solution of these inequalities, let us fix the values of the invariants $C_{111} = 1/2$, $C_{003} = 1/128$. The solution domain in the plane $C_{200} = C_{020}$ is presented in Fig. 1. The possible values of the invariants lie in the red domain near the vertex B of the curvilinear triangle ABC. The blue A–B and B–C lines are defined from (4.5) when the middle expression is equal to zero. Analogously, the green A–C line is defined from (4.7). The purple line separates the domain where the Grad matrix is positive (right upper part of the plane) from one where the Grad matrix is negative.

4.3 Peres-Horodecki Separability Criterion

If we transpose the second factors in the tensor products in the definition of density matrix ϱ (4.1), we get so-called partially transposed density matrix ϱ^{T_b} [22]. For our example (4.3), it reads as follows:

$$\varrho^{T_b} = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + \alpha + \beta + \gamma_3 & 0 & 0 & \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 \\ 0 & 1 + \alpha + \beta + \gamma_3 & \gamma_1 - \gamma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma_1 - \gamma_2 & 1 + \alpha + \beta + \gamma_3 & 0 \\ \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 & 0 & 0 & 1 + \alpha + \beta + \gamma_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Using ϱ^{T_b} and the derived system of the inequalities (4.4)–(4.8), we can formulate the separability criterion for two-qubit systems due to Peres–Horodecki [23, 24]:

The two-qubit the system is in a separable state if and only if the partially transposed density matrix ϱ^{T_b} satisfies the conditions for the density matrix.

The semipositivity domain for ϱ^{T_b} is defined by inequalities (4.4)–(4.8) up to a minor correction: the sign of $C_{003} = \gamma_1 \gamma_2 \gamma_3$ changes, because ϱ^{T_b} differs from ϱ only in the sign of γ_2 . The separability area (red domain) is shown in Fig. 2, where the A'B'C' curvilinear triangle corresponds to ϱ^{T_b} . Let us note that invariant C_{003} is nothing than the determinant of correlation

matrix C in the Fano form (4.1) of ρ . If C_{003} is zero, then correlation matrix C vanishes, while the ABC and A'B'C' triangles coincide. This means that all states are separable. With an increase in C_{003} , the correlations in the system become stronger and the separability area shrinks to zero.

5. Conclusions

The orbit space ρ/G of the local group action on an entangled system is an appropriate space for the definition of the entanglement measures. In a general case, ρ/G has a lower dimension than the state space of the system described by density matrix ρ . The semi-algebraic structure of the orbit space is completely determined by two kinds of inequalities in the elements of the integrity basis for the invariant ring $\mathbb{R}[\rho]^G$. The first kind originates from the Hermiticity and semi-positivity requirements on density matrices, while the second one follows from the orbit space description in the invariant theory. The Peres–Horodecki separability criterion for the two-qubit mixed states is considered as an example of application of the inequalities.

Fig. 1. Solution of Inequalities.

Fig. 2. Separability area.

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